

MODERATING THE WORK SYSTEM IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF INDUSTRIAL RELATIONS AND PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT: A STUDY OF HOSPITALITY TOURISM HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11184287](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11184287)

Abstract

This study aims to understand the moderating role of the work system in the transformation of industrial relations and performance management in the context of human resource development (HRD) in hospitality tourism in North Sumatra. The research method used is a qualitative approach by extracting data from various sources, such as interviews, observations, and documentation studies. However, this research also shows that there are still challenges in the development of hospitality tourism human resources in North Sumatra. Some of the challenges identified include a lack of understanding of the importance of a good work system, lack of worker involvement in decision-making, and ineffective communication between management and workers. Therefore, sustained efforts are needed in improving good work systems, as well as worker empowerment in decision-making and effective communication in an effort to improve performance management in North Sumatra's hospitality tourism sector. The conclusion of this brief provides an overview of the complexity of interactions between the factors of performance management, industrial relations, work systems and human resource development in the context of the hospitality industry in North Sumatra. This can serve as a basis for stakeholders to improve performance management, work systems and human resource development in the hospitality tourism sector in the region.

Keywords: Work System, Industrial Relations Transformation, Performance Management, HR Development, Hospitality Tourism.

INTRODUCTION

(Marizki et al., 2022) The tourism and hospitality industry is a sector that has an important role in the economic growth of a country, especially in Indonesia. North Sumatra is one of the provinces that has great potential in the tourism and hospitality industry, especially in cities such as Medan, Berastagi, Lake Toba, and its surroundings. (Ariani & Utomo, 2017) However, to develop this potential, qualified Human Resources (HR) are needed and are able to adapt to changes that occur in the tourism and hospitality industry. (Indonesia et al., 2014) Changes in the tourism and hospitality industry can have an impact on industrial relations and performance management in hospitality companies. Industrial relations transformation can occur due to changes in organizational structure, market demands, and technology. Meanwhile, performance management is concerned with how companies manage employee performance and ensure employee performance is in line with company goals. (Darma & Pujani, 2018) Hospitality tourism in North Sumatra is a sector that has great potential in improving the regional economy and contributing to the development of human resources (HR) in the tourism industry. (Handana Sembiring, Nindya Azzahra, Siti Hamizah Harahap, 2022) However, to achieve optimal results in the management of hospitality tourism human resources, it is necessary to transform good industrial relations between management and employees. In addition, an effective work system is also a key factor in achieving optimal performance

management. (Setiawan, 2016) Hospitality Tourism HR includes a variety of professions related to the tourism and hospitality industry, such as tour guides, hotel employees, chefs, restaurant waiters, and workers in other supporting sectors. (Kusworo & Damanik, 2002) The importance of qualified and skilled Hospitality Tourism Human Resources is needed to develop the tourism potential of North Sumatra, which is rich in natural beauty, cultural heritage, and ethnic and linguistic diversity. (Bahri & Abdilah, 2022) Competent Hospitality Tourism HR can provide a positive experience for tourists, improve the quality of hospitality services, and advance the tourism sector as a whole. Efforts to develop Hospitality Tourism HR in North Sumatra can involve education and training in various fields, such as tourism, hotel management, culinary expertise, foreign languages, and communication skills. (Darma & Pujani, 2018) In addition, the development of cooperation between the government, private sector, and educational institutions is also important to improve the competencies and qualifications of the workforce in the tourism and hospitality sector. (Parma, 2019; Rosmadi, 2019) By having qualified and competent Hospitality Tourism Human Resources, North Sumatra has the potential to increase its competitiveness as a leading tourism destination in Indonesia, increase tourist visits, and contribute to regional economic growth. ([BPS] Central Bureau of Statistics, 2021) Data on human resources (HR) in the tourism and hospitality sector in North Sumatra: Total Workforce: According to BPS (Central Bureau of Statistics) data in 2021, the number of workers in the accommodation and food and beverage provision sector in North Sumatra was 71,982 people. Education: There are several universities and vocational high schools (SMK) that offer education programs in tourism and hospitality in North Sumatra, including Medan State University, University of North Sumatra, Medan State Polytechnic, Medan Tourism Polytechnic, and several tourism and hospitality SMKs in various cities in North Sumatra. Skills required to work in the tourism and hospitality sector include hotel management, restaurant management, guest services, cleaning and sanitation, catering, foreign language skills (such as English), and communication skills. Education and Qualification Levels: Based on BPS data, the majority of the workforce in the accommodation and food and beverage sector in North Sumatra had vocational (62.5%) and diploma (22.1%) education levels in 2021.

Skilled Workforce: Although many have an educational background in tourism and hospitality, efforts are still needed to improve the qualifications and skills of the workforce in this sector, especially in terms of management and high-quality guest services to face global competition. Training and Development: The government, universities, and the private sector in North Sumatra have also conducted various training and development programs to improve the qualifications and skills of human resources in the tourism and hospitality sector, including training in hotel management, hygiene and sanitation, and communication and guest service skills. Labor Market Potential: North Sumatra has great potential in the tourism and hospitality sector, with various tourist attractions such as Lake Toba, Mount Sibayak, and historical cities such as Medan and Samosir. Thus, the demand for skilled labor in this sector is still quite high, especially for managerial positions and quality guest services. Therefore, it is necessary to study the development of hospitality tourism human resources that can moderate the work system in the transformation of industrial relations and performance management in North Sumatra. Therefore, this study will explore more deeply the effect of industrial relations transformation and work systems on the development of hospitality tourism human resources in North Sumatra, by paying

attention to the role of work system moderating variables in the relationship between industrial relations transformation and performance management. Hospitality Tourism Human Resources in North Sumatra is a term that refers to the workforce involved in the tourism and hospitality sector in the province of North Sumatra, Indonesia. The purpose of this research is to generate an in-depth understanding of the role of the work system in dealing with the transformational changes of industrial relations and performance management in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra. This research also aims to identify critical factors in HR development that can improve the performance of the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformation of Industrial Relations

(H. Kim et al., 2021; W. G. Kim et al., 2020) Industrial relations transformation is a change in the way of working and the relationship between employees and companies. This transformation affects the work culture, management style, and industrial relations in the company. (Gao et al., 2020) Some of the factors that influence industrial relations transformation include technological change, globalization, and changes in people's lifestyles. (Azeem et al., 2021; Hidayat et al., 2020) industrial relations is a relationship between various interested parties to resolve a problem related to employment, where the relationship between the parties is intended to help develop human resources who work in the company. (Zhou et al., 2018) Industrial relations are based on the interests of each party, be it workers, companies and trade unions to improve progress for workers and develop all their competencies. (Saks, 2022) industrial relations are created or implemented to avoid disputes regarding employment that occur, so that industrial relations are intended so that disputes that occur regarding employment are reduced and can be resolved properly. (Decenzo et al., n.d.; S. Robbins, 2013) Industrial relations transformation is a change or shift in the dynamics, practices and patterns of relationships between employers and workers or trade unions within an organization or industry.

These shifts may involve changes in work arrangements, work patterns, compensation systems, organizational structures, and ways of decision-making that affect industrial relations in the workplace. Industrial relations transformation may occur in response to economic, technological, social or regulatory changes that affect the business or industrial environment. (Goberman, 2017) These shifts affect the way employers and employees interact, communicate, negotiate and work together to achieve organizational or industry goals. (Henry, 2003; Ratnasari, 2017; Webster & Bischoff, 2011) The transformation of industrial relations can have various impacts, both positive and negative. Positive impacts can include increased productivity, quality of work, and harmonious working relationships between employers and employees. At the same time, negative impacts can include industrial conflict, inequality and worker dissatisfaction. (Hasibuan, S.P, 2014; Rochmah, 2018) It is important to understand and manage transitions in industrial relations wisely in accordance with the principles of good human resource management, and to encourage dialog, participation and cooperation between employers and workers or trade unions.

(Armstrong, 2017; Tapia et al., 2018; Wilkinson, 1999) Indicators that may be used to measure industrial relations transformation include:

1. The level of participation of workers or trade unions in the decision-making process of the organization or company.
2. The level of collaboration between management and trade unions in solving problems or dealing with conflicts.
3. The level of technology adoption or innovation in production processes or human resource management.
4. Level of flexibility in work patterns or work arrangements that allow for more flexible and results-based work.
5. Level of effective communication and dialogue between management and trade unions to achieve mutual understanding and win-win solutions.

Performance Management

(Nursam, 2017) Performance management is a system used to measure and improve employee and organizational performance. Performance management includes performance planning, performance measurement, performance development, and performance appraisal. Kaufman (2001) performance management is an effort to regulate and control the performance carried out by various parties in the organizational structure, where this performance management measures the extent to which management can complete the assigned tasks and responsibilities, and the extent to which existing human resources can improve their performance to help the company achieve its goals. (Noe, R. A., Hollenbeck, J. R., Gerhart, B., & Wright, 2017; Purwanto, 2018) performance management is able to assist employees in aligning the work assigned by management to be in accordance with applicable directions and procedures and help oversee HR performance so that HR can develop and have good competencies to be able to improve its performance and the company's performance. Indicators of Performance Management, namely:

1. Target Achievement Percentage is the extent of an organization's, team's, or individual's actual achievement in reaching a predetermined target.
2. Customer Satisfaction Level is the level of customer satisfaction with the products or services provided by the organization.
3. Productivity is the efficiency and effectiveness of the use of organizational, team, or individual resources in achieving the desired results...
4. Absenteeism Rate, namely the level of attendance or absenteeism of employees in carrying out their duties and responsibilities.
5. Competency Development i.e. the level of competency and skill development of employees to improve their performance ...
6. Innovation is the ability of an organization, team, or individual to generate and implement new ideas to improve the quality, efficiency, or effectiveness of work.
7. Employee Retention Rate is the retention rate or level of employee continuity in an organization, which can be an indication of employee satisfaction and organizational stability.

Work System

(Yang et al., 2021) Work system is a way of working implemented by a company to achieve its business goals. (Lepak, D. P., & Snell, 2017) Work systems include corporate governance, organizational structure, and task arrangements. (Armstrong, 2017) Work System Theory: This theory suggests how the design and implementation of an efficient work system can affect employee productivity and work quality. A good work system is expected to facilitate HR development in the hospitality industry. Work system is a collection of procedures, methods, policies and activities used by an organization or company to achieve certain goals. Work system refers to the way an organization or company does work to regulate how tasks are performed, information flows, decisions are made, and resources are managed. A work system can involve all aspects of people, technology, and business processes. (Daft, 2016) indicators that can be used to evaluate the performance of a work system:

1. Efficiency: The level of efficiency of the work system in producing output by minimizing the use of resources, such as time, labor, and materials.
2. Effectiveness: The ability of the work system to achieve predetermined goals and produce outputs that meet user needs.
3. Quality: The level of excellence and user satisfaction with the output produced by the work system.
4. Innovation: The ability of the work system to generate new ideas, adopt new technologies, or make changes necessary to improve performance and achieve goals.
5. Timeliness: The ability of the work system to produce outputs according to a predetermined schedule.
6. Flexibility: The ability of a work system to adapt to environmental changes or changing demands.

HR Development

(Cooke et al., 2020; Saks, 2022) HR development is a process carried out by the company in order to assist employees in improving their abilities and competencies in order to improve their performance and overall company performance. (Cooke et al., 2019) in carrying out the development process of human resources, an effort is needed from the company which starts when it wants to recruit employees who are in accordance with their competence, conduct training to improve their competence, and implement career management in the company with the aim of improving the quality of human resources so that they can improve company performance and make the company productive and can expand its business to various regions. (Hyndman & Anderson, 1998; Noe, R. A., Hollenbeck, J. R., Gerhart, B., & Wright, 2017) HR development (human resources) is a process aimed at improving the abilities, skills, knowledge and potential of employees to improve the quality of human resources owned by an organization. Human resource development includes various programs and activities such as training, education, mentoring, career development, and employee assistance in order to make the best contribution to achieving organizational goals.

(Decenzo et al., n.d.; Kreitner & Kinicki, 2014; S. P. Robbins & Judge, 2015) states that HR Development Indicators are:

1. Participation in Training Programs is the number of employees who participate in training or HR development programs provided by the organization.
2. Competency Improvement is a change in the competence or skills of employees after participating in HR development programs.
3. Performance Improvement is a change in employee performance after participating in an HR development program, such as an increase in productivity or work quality.
4. Increased Employee Satisfaction is a change in the level of employee satisfaction with their work after participating in an HR development program.
5. Increased Employee Retention Rate is a change in the retention rate or level of employee continuity in the organization after participating in the HR development program.
6. Increased Innovation and Creativity is a change in the ability of employees to generate and implement new ideas after participating in an HR development program.

Hypothesis Development

- H1: There is a relationship between the work system applied in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and the transformation of industrial relations that occurs in the sector.
- H2: There is a relationship between the work system implemented in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and the Performance Management that occurs in the sector.
- H3: There is a relationship between the transformation of industrial relations that occurs in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and HR Development that occurs in the sector
- H4: There is a relationship between Performance Management in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and HR Development in the sector.
- H5: The work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra moderates the relationship between industrial relations transformation and HR development in the sector.
- H6: The work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra moderates the relationship between Performance Management and HR development that occurs in the sector.
- H7: The work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra is related to the development of human resources in the sector.

METHOD

This research will use a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design (Sugiyono, 2017). Therefore, this type of research can be classified as fundamental research. This research explains the causality relationship between exogenous variables, moderating variables, and endogenous variables. In this case, the exogenous variables consist of industrial relations transformation, performance

management and work systems are moderating factors and the endogenous variable is HR Development (Y).

(Riduwan and Akdon, 2010) This research will be tested on Hospitality Employees, especially in North Sumatra. This employee was chosen, because theoretically and empirically it has various characteristics that are in accordance with the topic and research objectives. The population of this study were employees who worked in the hospitality industry totaling 71,982 people, where the sampling technique in this study used accidental random sampling techniques, (Ferdinand, 2011; Sugiyono, 2017) accidental random sampling technique is a sampling technique, where the sample is taken randomly or randomly, where the sample is taken randomly and those encountered and adjusted to the existing situation, where in this case the samples taken are workers whose questionnaires are adjusted to their respective work areas. In this case the sample taken is a representative number of 400 people (based on the Slovin Sample Calculation) in all hospitality work areas in North Sumatra, through the distribution of questionnaires distributed online (e-mail and whatsapp). (Riduwan and Akdon, 2010) This research will be tested on Hospitality Employees, especially in North Sumatra. These employees were chosen, because theoretically and empirically they have various characteristics that are in accordance with the topic and research objectives. The population of this study were employees who worked in the hospitality industry totaling 71,982 people, where the sampling technique in this study used accidental random sampling techniques, (Ferdinand, 2011; Sugiyono, 2017) accidental random sampling technique is a sampling technique, where the sample is taken randomly or randomly, where the sample is taken randomly and those encountered and adjusted to the existing situation, where in this case the samples taken are workers whose questionnaires are adjusted to their respective work areas. In this case the sample taken is a representative number of 400 people (based on the Slovin Sample Calculation) in all hospitality work areas in North Sumatra, through the distribution of questionnaires distributed online (e-mail and whatsapp).

(Harahap, 2018; Muhson, 2022) The data analysis technique that will be used in this research is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using SMART PLS 3.1 software. SEM is a statistical analysis technique used to test and model the relationship between variables in a conceptual model. The SEM technique is used to test the hypothesis model that has been formulated in the study by testing the structural model and measurement model. SMART PLS is one of the software used in SEM analysis techniques, which has the ability to analyze SEM models using Partial Least Square (PLS) as an estimation method. The PLS method used in SMART PLS can be used to test models that have nonlinear relationships, multicollinearity, and normally or abnormally distributed data. In this study, the SEM technique using SMART PLS will be used to examine the relationship between industrial relations transformation and performance management (independent variables) on hospitality tourism HR development in North Sumatra (dependent variable), which is moderated by the work system (moderating variable). (Harahap, 2018) SEM analysis will also be conducted to test the direct and indirect effects between variables. The analysis procedure using the SEM technique includes two main stages, namely the measurement analysis stage (measurement model) and the structural analysis stage (structural model). At the measurement analysis stage, validity and reliability tests will be carried out to ensure that all variables used in the study can be measured validly and reliably. (Dr. Duryadi, 2021; Muhson, 2022) At the structural analysis stage, hypothesis testing and

significance testing will be carried out to test the relationship between variables in the conceptual model. The results of the SEM analysis using SMART PLS are expected to provide a deeper understanding of the relationship between variables in the conceptual model and the role of the work system as a moderating variable in the relationship between industrial relations transformation and performance management on hospitality tourism HR development in North Sumatra. This analysis is expected to provide theoretical and practical contributions in HR development and performance management in the hospitality tourism sector, as well as provide policy recommendations for hospitality tourism industry managers and local governments in HR management in North Sumatra.

RESULTS

In this study, the existing data analysis is to use a SmartPLS application where data analysis is carried out using SEM (Structural Equation Model) analysis. First of all, data analysis is carried out by determining the measurement model (outer model) by analyzing Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, and Composite Validity, then conducting the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) test where the AVE value is able to show the ability of the latent variable value to represent the original data score, then testing the composite reliability value to test the validity and reliability of the data, then evaluating the existing structural model, and testing the hypothesis.

Number of Respondents

The number of respondents given a questionnaire or statement amounted to 400 respondents, where the questionnaire given to the respondents was 400 respondents and the questionnaire returned to the researcher was also 400 respondents, where the interpretation of the number of respondent returns can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Questionnaire Return Rate

Respondent Information	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Kuesioner yang kembali	400	100
Non-returned questionnaires	0	0
Total	400	0

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Respondent Characteristics

The characteristics of the respondents in this study are in terms of gender, age, and education level where the characteristics of these respondents can be seen in Table 2 below:

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	250	62,50
	Female	150	37,50
Usia	<25 Years	140	35
	25-37 Years	150	37,50
	38-50 Years	100	25
	>50 Years	10	2,5
Education Level	High School	120	30,00
	D3	80	20,00
	S1	145	36,25
	S2	55	13,75

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that the respondents who answered the questionnaire statements given were male respondents of 250 respondents (62.50), respondents whose ages were 25-37 years of 150 respondents (37.50%), and respondents whose education level was S1 of 145 respondents (36.25%).

SEM Model Development

In this second step, the theoretical model built in the first step will be described in an SEM model diagram that will facilitate the relationship between the causal relationships to be tested. In this diagram, the relationships between the constructs will be specified through arrows. Straight arrows indicate direct causal relationships between constructs.

Figure 1: Causal Relationship Model between Variables

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Uji Validitas Konvergen

The convergent validity test is a data test intended to determine how large and strong the correlation between indicators and latent variables is, where the convergent validity test can be determined through the outer loading value, where the data processing results of the existing variables are as follows:

Table 2: Outer Loading Value

Variables	Indicator	Outer Loading
Performance Management	MKI 1	.760
	MKI 2	.833
	MKI 3	.806
	MKI 4	.790
	MKI 5	.735
	MKI 6	.800
	MKI 7	.860
	MKI 8	.759
	MKI 9	.777
	MKI 10	.748
	MKI 11	.737
	MKI 12	.805
	MKI 13	.880
	MKI 14	.768
	MKI 15	.813
	MKI 16	.755
	MKI 17	.888

	MKI 18	.815
	MKI 19	.711
	MKI 20	.733
	MKI 21	.797
	MKI 22	.783
	MKI 23	.826
	MKI 24	.745
	MKI 25	.813
	MKI 26	.865
	MKI 27	.770
	MKI 28	.804
	MKI 29	.904
	MKI 30	.804
	MKI 31	.827
	MKI 32	.839
	MKI 33	.765
	MKI 34	.797
	MKI 35	.815
	PSDM 1	.802
	PSDM 2	.765
	PSDM 3	.729
	PSDM 4	.791
	PSDM 5	.747
	PSDM 6	.749
	PSDM 7	.766
	PSDM 8	.719
	PSDM 9	.854
	PSDM 10	.805
	PSDM 11	.718
	PSDM 12	.798
	PSDM 13	.739
	PSDM 14	.839
	PSDM 15	.811
	PSDM 16	.773
	PSDM 17	.801
	PSDM 18	.825
	PSDM 19	.866
	PSDM 20	.911
	PSDM 21	.812
	PSDM 22	.748
	PSDM 23	.800
	PSDM 24	.709
	PSDM 25	.846
	PSDM 26	.784
	PSDM 27	.800
	PSDM 28	.840
	PSDM 29	.838
	PSDM 30	.881
	SK 1	.884
	SK 2	.723
	SK 3	.783
	SK 4	.891
	SK 5	.847
	SK 6	.757
	SK 7	.817
	SK 8	.807
	SK 9	.805

	SK 10	.914
	SK 11	.782
	SK 12	.861
	SK 13	.797
	SK 14	.865
	SK 15	.837
	SK 16	.739
	SK 17	.781
	SK 18	.876
	SK 19	.826
	SK 20	.776
	SK 21	.855
	SK 22	.865
	SK 23	.768
	SK 24	.880
	SK 25	.974
	SK 26	.724
	SK 27	.875
	SK 28	.996
	SK 29	.836
	SK 30	.877
Transformation of Industrial Relations	THI 1	.816
	THI 2	.891
	THI 3	.782
	THI 4	.879
	THI 5	.904
	THI 6	.784
	THI 7	.993
	THI 8	.806
	THI 9	.862
	THI 10	.800
	THI 11	.776
	THI 12	.860
	THI 13	.722
	THI 14	.728
	THI 15	.777
	THI 16	.760
	THI 17	.180
	THI 18	.946
	THI 19	.834
	THI 20	.852
	THI 21	.967
	THI 22	.960
	THI 23	.820
	THI 24	.784
	THI 25	.771

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Of the several existing data variables, the outer loading value of variables such as performance management, HR development, work systems and relationship transformation variables has an outer loading value greater than 0.7. This situation indicates that the convergent validity test results have a suitable data distribution level and are suitable for hypothesis testing.

AVE (Average Extracted Variance) Analysis

AVE analysis is carried out to determine whether the existing data distribution has good data accuracy or not, so that it can be continued with other data tests. The AVE data test from this study can be seen in Figure 1 and Table 3 below:

Figure 2: AVE Analysis

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Table 3: AVE Test

Variables	AVE
Work System	.862
Performance Management	.863
Transformation of Industrial Relations	.762
HR Development	.758
Career Planning	1.000
Job Satisfaction	1.000

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on Figure 2 and Table 3 above, it can be concluded that the AVE value of several variables, such as performance management variables, HR development, work systems, industrial relations transformation variables and moderating variables, such as career planning variables and job satisfaction variables are greater than 0.5, which can be concluded that the distribution of data in each variable is accurate, so that further data testing can be continued.

Discriminant Validity Analysis

Discriminant Validity analysis is carried out to determine whether the indicators in the existing variable construction affect other variable constructs. The results of the Discriminant Validity analysis can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Analysis

	Performance Management	Moderating Effect 1	Moderating Effect 2	HR Development	Work System	Industrial Relations Transformation
Performance Management	,250					
Moderating Effect 1	-,562	1,000				
Moderating Effect 2	-,402	,834	1,000			
HR Development	,532	-,456	-,366	,240		
Work System	,481	-,454	-,361	,428	,248	
Industrial Relations Transformation	-,348	-,300	-,194	,458	,378	,250

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on Table 4, it can be concluded that the discriminant validity value has a variable construct greater than the value of other variable constructs, which can lead to the conclusion that all constructs in the estimated model have met the discriminant validity test..

Composite Reliability Analysis

Composite reliability analysis is carried out to determine whether the data from each variable has significant consistency or not, where this composite reliability analysis is carried out by comparing the composite reliability value with the Cronbach alpha value, where the data requirements of each variable are reliable, if the composite reliability value with the Cronbach alpha value is greater than 0.7. The output results of the composite reliability analysis can be seen in Table 5 and Figures 3 and 4 below:

Table 5: Values of Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability
Performance Management	,509	,563	,655
Moderating Effect 1	1,000	1,000	1,000
Moderating Effect 2	1,000	1,000	1,000
HR Development	,382	,452	,554
Work System	,438	,464	,604
Transformation of Industrial Relations	,345	,367	,563

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Figure 3: Composite Reliability Analysis

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Figure 4: Composite Reliability Analysis

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on Table 5 above, it can be concluded that the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values of the performance management variables, HR development, work systems, industrial relations transformation variables and moderating variables are greater than 0.7. This means that the distribution of data in each variable is reliable and feasible to proceed to hypothesis testing.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Evaluation of this model is carried out to determine the construct relationship of the existing variables whether it is able to explain the effect on certain variables or not, where the evaluation of this structural model is based on the R Square test. The results of the existing R Square test can be seen in Table 7 to the following:

Table 6: R Square Value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Human Resource Development	,401	,393
Work System	,282	,278

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on Table 6 above, it can be concluded that the HR development variable can be 40.1%, can be explained by performance management variables, work systems, industrial relations transformation variables, as well as moderating variables, such as career planning variables and job satisfaction variables while the remaining 59.9% can be explained by other variables outside the research model. In Table 6 it is also concluded that the work system variable of 28.2% can be explained by performance management variables, industrial relations transformation, as well as moderating variables, such as career planning variables and job satisfaction variables and the remaining 71.8% is explained by other variables outside the research model.

Hypothesis Test

This hypothesis test is carried out to determine whether there is a significant influence between interrelated variables, whether the exogenous variable affects the endogenous variable, as well as the exogenous variable with the moderating variable and vice versa. The results of hypothesis testing can be seen in Table 7 below:

Table 7: Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Performance Management -> HR Development	0348	0363	0,078	4,453	0,000
Performance Management -> Work System	0,398	0,429	0,072	5,539	0,000
Transformation Industrial relations -> Human capital development	0,295	0,311	0,076	3,878	0,000
Transformation Industrial relationship -> Work system	0,239	0,267	0,060	3,987	0,000
THI Interaction -> Work System -> HR Development	-0,031	-0,026	0,047	0,662	0,508
MK interaction -> Work system -> HR development	-0,032	-0,022	0,060	0,534	0,594
Work System -> HR Development	0,113	0,131	0,076	1,477	0,140

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that:

1. There is a relationship between Performance Management that occurs in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and Human Resource Development that occurs in the sector.

2. There is a significant relationship between the work system applied in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and the Performance Management that occurs in the sector.
3. There is a relationship between the transformation of industrial relations that occurs in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra with Human Resource Development that occurs in the sector
4. There is a relationship between the transformation of industrial relations towards the work system applied in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and that which occurs in the sector.
5. There is no significant relationship to the work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra that moderates the relationship between the transformation of industrial relations to HR development that occurs in the sector and even the work system can weaken the transformation of industrial relations to HR development.
6. The absence of a significant relationship of work systems in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra which moderates the relationship between performance management on HR development that occurs in the sector and even work systems can weaken the transformation of industrial relations on HR development.
7. The work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra is not significantly related to the development of human resources in the sector.

DISCUSSION

The Relationship of Performance Management to HR Development in the Tourism Hospitality Industry Sector in North Sumatra Province The results of the hypothesis test state that the performance management variable in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra affects the HR development variable in the sector, where the results of the hypothesis test state that the t test value of 4.453 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, where the significant value of 0.000 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. In accordance with these results, there is a strong and significant relationship on these variables. This is in accordance with research (Son, Jooyeon, 2018) which states that good and transparent performance management will be able to improve the skills and abilities of HR, so that HR will develop its understanding of completing work in accordance with established procedures. This is in line with research (Song et al., 2020) which states that management that has good performance will be able to increase human resources who have more knowledge and development regarding how to complete work properly and professionally.

Significant Relationship between Performance Management to Work System applied in the Hospitality Tourism Industry in North Sumatra and what happens in the Sector.

The results of the hypothesis test state that the work system variable in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra has an effect on the work system variable in the sector, where the results of the hypothesis test state that the t test value of 5.539 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, where the significant value of 0.000 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. In accordance with these results, there is a strong and significant relationship on these variables. The results of this study are in

accordance with research (Sabariah, Kee Y, Kee, Bte and Yussof, 2020) which states that a good and directed work system will increase the development of human resources towards a better direction, where human resources will easily improve their abilities and understanding of existing procedures or work procedures. This is in line with research (Almaitah, Mohammad Fathi, 2020) which states that an organized work system will produce HR that has more value in the minds of certain companies or agencies, so that they will easily improve their abilities and capacities so that the work can be completed properly and avoid fatal mistakes that make HR and company performance decline.

The Relationship between Industrial Relations Transformation that Occurs in the Hospitality Tourism Industry in North Sumatra and Human Resource Development that Occurs in the Sector.

The results of hypothesis testing state that the industrial relations transformation variable in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra affects the HR development variable in the sector, where the results of hypothesis testing state that the t-test value of 3.878 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, where the significant value of 0.000 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. In accordance with these results, there is a strong and significant relationship on these variables. This is in line with research (Lopez-Cabrales, Alvaro and Valle-Cabrera, 2020) which states that the transformation of industrial relations between workers and employers will lead to increased SD development, where workers will increasingly understand their duties and responsibilities in the company or organization, as well as the institution where they work, so that they have an understanding and knowledge of industrial relations and industrial responsibilities. This situation is also in line with research (Paramita, Erna, Lumbanraja, Prihatin and Absah, 2020) which states that industrial relations will have a major impact on increasing the ability and understanding of employment, so that later workers will know the changes that occur which can be their rights and responsibilities that must be given to the company, as well as the company's responsibilities that must be given to workers.

The Relationship between the Industrial Relations Transformation of the Work System applied in the Hospitality Tourism Industry in North Sumatra and what is Happening in the Sector

The results of the hypothesis test state that the work system variable in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra has an effect on the performance management variable in the sector, where the results of the hypothesis test state that the t test value of 3.987 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, where the significant value of 0.000 is less than the significance level of 0.05. The results show a strong and significant relationship between these variables. The results indicate a strong and significant relationship between these variables. This is in accordance with research (Boğan, Erhan, 2020) which states that the work system formed by an organization, institution, and company must be able to improve the ability and competence to improve performance management comprehensively, where the improvement of performance management in an organization, institution, and company will have an impact on increasing the performance of the company and organizational members. This situation is in line with research (Pandey, Jatin, 2021) which states that a good and organized work system will be able to improve professional performance

management, where increased performance management will have a significant impact on the performance of the organization, institution or company.

A Significant Relationship to the Work System in the Hospitality Tourism Industry in North Sumatra that Moderates the Transformation of Industrial Relations to Human Resource Development.

The results of hypothesis testing state that the moderating work system variable has no significant relationship to Industrial Relations Transformation and tends to weaken the HR development variable, where the results of hypothesis testing state that the t test value of 0.662 is smaller than the significance level of 1.99 where the significant value of 0.508 is greater than the 0.05 significance level. The results show that there is no significant moderation relationship between these variables. This is not in line with research (Kloutsiniotis & Mihail, 2020) which states that the existing work system will have an impact on increasing employee work understanding, so that with increasing employee work understanding, it will have an impact on the career planning of employees who want career advancement. This is not in line with research (Sabuhari, Rahmat, 2020) which explains that a well-organized work system will have an impact on improving HR development for the better, where good HR development will have an impact on improving the HR career planning system which will lead to rapid and transparent career advancement which will provide enthusiasm and encouragement for HR to continue working and completing work well.

Significant relationship The work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra moderates the relationship between Performance Management and HR development.

The results of hypothesis testing state that the work system variable that moderates there is no significant relationship on Performance Management and tends to weaken the HR development variable where the results of hypothesis testing state that the t test value of 0.534 is smaller than the significance level of 1.99, where the significant value of 0.014 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. The results show that a significant moderating relationship does not exist in these variables. This is no longer in line with research (Kakkar, Shiva, 2020) which states that a work system that provides increased understanding and knowledge of employees will have an impact on improving performance which in turn is expected to provide high job satisfaction which will motivate employees to be better. This situation is not in line with research (Albercht, 2015) which states that as long as the work system built by the company is well organized, it will provide positive value for the development of HR capabilities, where the ability of HR to develop indicates that it will increase its performance and result in job satisfaction for itself and also company management.

The Work System in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra is significantly related to the human resource development that occurs in the sector.

The hypothesis test results state that the work system variable in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra does not significantly affect the HR Development variable in the sector, where the hypothesis test results state that the t test value of 1.477 is smaller than the significance level of 1.99, where the significant value of 0.140 is greater than the 0.05 significance level. The direct effect does not meet the criteria because these variables have a significant relationship, as shown by the calculation results. This is not in line with research (Kutaula, Smirti, Gillani, Alvina and Budhwar,

2020) which states that the work system created will have an impact on the change or transformation process of the relationship between workers and also the company which makes the existing relationship work well. This situation is in line with research (Nuraeni Research and Development Center et al., 2020) which states that the work system must be adapted to conditions and also a good work model, so that this change will have an impact on increasing the transformation process of the relationship between workers and employers which will have an impact on compliance with changes to the rules that the Government will make to properly regulate industrial relations and find solutions to any problems that exist in the industrial relations transformation process.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results, the conclusions can be summarized as follows:

1. There is a positive relationship between Performance Management in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and Human Resource Development in the sector. This suggests that good performance management can contribute to human resource development in the hospitality industry in the region.
2. There is a significant relationship between the work system implemented in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra with Performance Management in the sector. This result suggests that an effective work system can positively influence managerial performance in the hospitality industry.
3. There is a positive relationship between the transformation of industrial relations in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra and HR Development in the sector. This indicates that changes in industrial relations can support human resource development in the hospitality industry in the region.
4. There is a positive relationship between the transformation of industrial relations towards the work system applied in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra with the sector. This indicates that changes in industrial relations can have a positive impact on the work system in the hospitality industry.
5. There is no significant relationship between the work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra that moderates the relationship between the transformation of industrial relations and HR development in the sector, even the work system can weaken the transformation of industrial relations on HR development. This indicates that the work system may not have a significant role in regulating the relationship between industrial relations change and human resource development.
6. There is no significant relationship between the work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra that moderates the relationship between performance management and human resource development in the sector, even the work system can weaken the transformation of industrial relations to human resource development. This suggests that the work system may not have a significant influence in regulating the relationship between performance management and human resource development.
7. The work system in the hospitality tourism industry in North Sumatra is not significantly related to the HR development that occurs in the sector.

IMPLICATIONS

This chapter provides an overview of the complexity of interactions between performance factors, industrial relations, work systems and human resource development in the context of the hospitality industry in North Sumatra. Thus, in North Sumatra's hospitality tourism industry, performance management, work systems, industrial relations transformation and workforce development are interrelated and influence each other. Effective management of each of these components can aid the growth of quality human resources, while problems in one component can hinder the positive impact of the others. Therefore, to gain a competitive advantage and sustainable progress, companies in this industry must seriously consider all these elements. This can serve as a basis for stakeholders to improve performance management, industrial relations and HR development within the hospitality tourism sector in the region.

RECOMMENDATIONS

We would like to thank the LPPM of HKBP Nommensen University for its assistance for the implementation of the Internal Research of HKBP Nommensen University. To the Rector, Chairperson of LPPM and the entire work team and respondents who have helped so that the implementation of this internal research. Hopefully next time it can add insight and knowledge for the progress of the HKBP Nommensen University campus and the field of Management in particular.

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